

Screening Of Different Carbon Sources For Staphylococcus Aureus

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Abstract— The aim of this study was to screen different carbon sources for *Staphylococcus aureus* to identify potential replacements for glucose. Glucose is a commonly used carbon source in microbial culture media, however, it can be expensive and may not be readily available in certain regions. In this study, a total of 6 different carbon sources were tested, including lactose, maltose, sucrose, fructose, glucose, n-hexane, toluene. The growth rate and biomass production of *S. aureus* were compared between each carbon source and glucose, which served as the control. The results showed that *S. aureus* was able to grow on all of the tested carbon sources, however, there were significant differences in the growth rates and biomass production between each carbon source. Specifically, fructose were found to be the most promising replacements for glucose, as they were able to support similar growth rates and biomass production as glucose.

Keywords: carbon source, replacement, *Staphylococcus aureus*, utilization

I. INTRODUCTION

Environment on earth, including soil, water, air, and even inside other organisms. Microorganisms play a vital role in many different ecosystems and are essential for the survival of life on earth. They are involved in processes such as nutrient cycling, decomposition, and the production of food, drugs, and other useful products. While some microorganisms can be harmful to humans and other organisms, many are beneficial and play important roles in human health and medicine. For example, some bacteria in our gut help us digest food, while others are used to produce antibiotics and vaccines, form for example, *Staphylococcus aureus* germs, for instance, are found in spherical clusters. While tiny, microorganisms are strong and sophisticated.[1]

Every organism must be able to locate all of the components needed for cellular biosynthesis and energy production in its surroundings. The nutrients and carbon sources requirements are the substances and components of this environment that are used for bacterial development. In culture media that are created to provide all the necessary nutrients in solution for bacterial development, many bacteria can be grown in the laboratory[2].

A bacterium needs a source of carbon, nitrogen, water, and inorganic salts in order to grow and live. To sustain these necessities for life, bacteria have strong systems that enable them to use a wide variety of substances. Because bacteria need carbon metabolism to produce ATP as well as to provide precursors for all of the biosynthetic reactions necessary for life, carbon sources are essential. Although some metabolic pathways may vary slightly across various phylogenetic kingdoms, metabolism is a conserved process in every living cell [3]. Glycolysis, the pentose phosphate pathway, and the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle, also referred to as the Krebs cycle or the citric acid cycle, are the three primary routes in bacterial central metabolism. . For cell development and the production of products, carbon sources are primarily used. The formation of the secondary metabolites would be suppressed by the presence of carbon sources, so the production of the secondary metabolites typically happens when carbon sources are scarce in the media[3].

The availability of resources has been hypothesised to affect *staphylococcus aureus* growth, production, and community organisation. The purpose of this study was to examine how the community of *staphylococcus aureus* was affected by six distinct pertinent carbon sources., so the production of the secondary metabolites typically happens when carbon sources are scarce in the media[3].

Staphylococcus aureus can survive At temperatures between 15° and 45°C and NaCl amounts as high as 15%, Extended shots above 42°C or below 10°C are not advised, though. Over a week of storage at 4°C is not recommend for plates. *S. aureus* is immune to high osmolarity, detergents, and alcohol because of its highly cross-linked peptidoglycan. Because *S. aureus* can metabolise luria bertani agar, luria bertani agar with a 7.5% NaCl content has been used as a selective medium. On all rich media, including tryptic soy agar (TSA) at 37°C, brain heart infusion (BHI) agar, and Luria Bertani (LB) agar, *s. aureus* forms the distinctive gold-colored colonies. This organism also generates the yellow pigment staphyloxanthin[4].

Glucose, which is typically an excellent carbon source for development in bacteria and other microorganisms, interferes with the formation of many antibiotics because "too much of a good thing can be harmful." The former is used first to create cells in media that contain mixtures of quickly and slowly used carbon sources, but little to no antibiotics are synthesised. The "second-best" carbon supply is used for idiolite formation after the quickly assimilated compound is exhausted [5].

The screening of different carbon sources, including fructose, maltose, lactose, n-hexane, toluene, and sucrose, is the main focus of the work. Growth curve analyses were used to assess the influence of these factors. The carbon source must be optimised in order for these strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* to improve yield efficiency. Based on the comparative data, the carbon sources were individually screened for each of the aforementioned strains. For each instance, generation time and a specific growth rate were calculated [6].

II. Materials and methods

II.I. STAIN SELECTION

Staphylococcus aureus bacterial strains were purchased from Parul Sevashram Hospital (Parul University, Vadodra). Working stocks were made from the obtained strain and then used for additional experiments. The strains were kept at 40°C while being cultured on agar slants and plates at 30°C for tests. Periodically, sub-culturing was done with glycerol stocks.

II.II. MEDIA SELECTION

The strain *Staphylococcus aureus* were grown on three different nutrient-rich media. Nutrient broth (NB) medium contains 10 g l⁻¹ peptone, 10 g l⁻¹ beef extract and 5 g l⁻¹ of NaCl (pH 7.3 ± 0.1). Luria Bertani (LB) broth comprises of 5 g l⁻¹ sodium chloride, 5 g l⁻¹ yeast extract, and 10 g l⁻¹ of casein enzymic hydrolysate with pH 7.0 ± 0.2. Mineral salt Medium (MS) contains 1.73 g l⁻¹ dipotassium hydrogen phosphate (K₂HPO₄), 0.68 g l⁻¹ Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄), 0.1 g l⁻¹ Magnesium sulfate heptahydrate (MgSO₄ · 7H₂O), 4 g l⁻¹ Sodium chloride (NaCl), 0.03 g l⁻¹ Ferrus ammonium sulphate, 0.02 g l⁻¹ Calcium chloride (CaCl₂ · 2H₂O), 5 g l⁻¹ Glucose (C₆H₁₂O₆) in distilled water. The pH of the media was adjusted by adding either HCl (1N) or KOH (2N) solution prior to sterilization. The culture media were autoclaved at 121°C for 20 min.

II.III. MEDIA AND GROWTH STUDY

The media chosen in section media selection were the subjects of the growth studies. From a freshly streaked Luria-Bertani (LB) agar plate, one colony of *Staphylococcus aureus* was selected and utilised to inoculate 10 ml of LB medium for overnight growth at 30°C, 150 rpm in a shaking incubator. A 50 ml flask of NB, LB, and MS medium was inoculated with a total volume of 1-2 ml from this starter culture with an adjusted OD of 0.2 while it was being shaken at 30°C and 150 rpm. The trials were carried out in triplicate, and a control flask with pure sterile medium was also used. By taking spectrophotometric measurements of optical densities at 620 nm (OD₆₂₀) every two hours, growth was evaluated. The experiment was carried out for 24 hours for *Staphylococcus aureus*.

II.IV. CARBON SOURCE SCREENING METHOD

N-hexane, lactose, fructose, sucrose, maltose, and toluene were the six carbon sources selected for screening. To a final concentration of 10 g l⁻¹, each carbon source was added in place of the MS medium's glucose as the only carbon source. Since n-hexane and toluene are combustible and cannot be sterilised, the media had to be cleaned before introducing them as carbon sources. During the production of the media and subsequent sterilisation, additional carbon sources were introduced. There were three duplicates of each experiment. Via the addition of a corresponding carbon source comprising sterile MS medium, a control experiment was completed without the use of microbes. Every two hours, optical density was measured using a spectrophotometer set to 620 nm (OD₆₂₀). For *Staphylococcus aureus*, the test was run for 24 hours.

III. RESULT

III.I. GROWTH CURVE STUDIES—*S.aureus* in three different media was measured with an absorbance at 620 nm and plotted at different time intervals. (Fig-1)

III.II. Growth in LB medium: *S.aureus* in the LB medium has an initial OD of (0.89). After 4 hours, the OD is at (1.33), indicating that the bacteria are growing in the medium. The growth rate increased after 6 hours with an OD of (1.62). After 8 hours, the bacterial growth continued to increase, reaching an OD of (1.67). *S.aureus* OD was determined after 10 hours (1.49).

III.III. Growth in NB medium: In the first few hours, *S.aureus* in NB medium has an OD of (0.87). After 4 hours, the OD was (1.15), indicating that the bacteria was growing in the medium. The growth rate is increased to an OD of (1.47) after 6 hours. Bacterial growth is still increasing after 8 hours, with an OD of (1.71). The OD of *staphylococcus aureus* after 10 hours was 1.65.

III.IV. Growth in mineral salt medium: *S.aureus* in the early hours of MSM, an OD of (1.37) is displayed. It has an OD of (1.45) after 4 hours, indicating that the bacteria are growing in the medium. The growth rate increases to an OD of (1.51) after 6 hours. The bacterial growth is still active after 8 hours, with an OD of (1.55). The OD of *S.aureus* decreased slightly after 10 hours to (1.53).

Figure 1: Growth curve of staphylococcus aureus on different media

III.V. GROWTH RATES OF S.AUREUS ON DIFFERENT CARBON SOURCES

The growth of *S.aureus* was measured at various points using n-hexane, fructose, toluene, sucrose, lactose, and maltose as the sole carbon source. *S.aureus* growth on various carbon sources was measured using an absorbance at 620 nm and plotted over time (Fig-2). In the first two hours of day one, *Staphylococcus aureus* demonstrates maximal growth in MS medium supplemented with glucose, reaching an optical density (OD) of 1.7. The growth rate of *S.aureus* in fructose-containing medium is similar to that observed in glucose-containing medium, with an OD of 1.9. Subsequently, *s.aureus* exhibits good growth rates in sucrose-containing medium, reaching an OD of 1.2, followed by maltose-containing medium, with an OD of 1.05, and lactose-containing medium, with an OD of 0.9. However, growth of *s.aureus* is minimal in MS medium containing N-hexane and toluene, with an OD of 0 and 0.04, respectively. After four hours of growth, the growth rate of *S. aureus* in MS medium containing glucose, fructose, sucrose, maltose, and lactose is 1.03, 1.78, 1.17, 1.09 and 1.02 respectively. The toluene-containing growth medium exhibits an increased growth rate at an OD of 0.6, while the N-hexane-containing growth medium shows a increase in growth rate at an OD of 0.07. After six hours of growth, all carbon-containing media exhibit a decline in growth rate, except for the toluene-containing medium, which demonstrates continued growth at an OD of 0.4. At eight hours of growth, the growth rate of *S. Aureus* is increased in the toluene-containing media, while all other carbon-containing media show a decline in growth rate.

Figure 2: Growth rate and generation time of *staphylococcus aureus* on various carbon source

DAY-1

III.V.I. DAY – 2

On the second day of experimentation, the growth rate of *S.aureus* displayed a decrease when cultivated in MS medium containing all carbon sources. Furthermore, no growth *s.aureus* was observed in the MS medium supplemented with N-hexane. The medium containing sucrose showed a slower rate of decline in growth compared to the medium containing fructose. Conversely, the growth rate of *s.aureus* in N-hexane-containing media remained constant throughout the experimental period. These observations suggest

that the carbon source composition of the medium plays a critical role in the growth of *S. aureus*, with different carbon sources affecting the growth rate differently. (Fig-3)

Figure 3:Growth rate and generation time of *staphylococcus aureus* on various carbon source [DAY 2]

IV. DISCUSSION

Screening different carbon sources for *Staphylococcus aureus* is an essential aspect of microbiology research. The goal of the screening is to identify the preferred carbon sources that can be used by the bacteria for their growth and metabolism. This information can be useful in developing treatment strategies for infections caused by *staphylococcus aureus*.

The screening process involves testing different carbon sources, *Staphylococcus aureus* is a gram-positive bacterium that can use a variety of carbon sources for its growth and metabolism. Glucose is the most commonly used carbon source for *Staphylococcus aureus*, but there is a growing interest in identifying alternative carbon sources that can replace glucose. Such as sugars, lactose, fructose, maltose, sucrose, toluene, n-hexane, to determine which ones support the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*. This is done by inoculating a culture medium with the bacteria and adding the carbon source of interest. The culture is then incubated at an optimal temperature for *Staphylococcus aureus* growth and observed for bacterial growth. The use of alternative carbon sources is important because glucose availability can be limited in some environments, such as in the human body during infection. Additionally, the overuse of glucose in bacterial cultures can lead to the production of unwanted by-products that can interfere with downstream applications. There are several carbon sources that have been studied as potential replacements for glucose in *Staphylococcus aureus* cultures. These include lactose, sucrose, fructose, maltose, n-hexane, and toluene. The choice of carbon source depends on several factors, including the availability of the carbon source, the metabolic capabilities of the bacteria, and the specific application of the bacterial culture. The screening process can be time-consuming and requires a large number of experiments to test all the possible carbon sources. However, the results of the screening can provide valuable insights into the metabolic capabilities of *Staphylococcus aureus*, which can be used to develop targeted therapies for infections caused by the bacteria.

VI. CONCLUSION

The screening of different carbon sources for *Staphylococcus aureus* revealed that some carbon sources can support the growth of this bacterium better than others. For example, fructose and Maltose were found to be good alternatives to glucose as they supported the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* to a similar extent as glucose. On the other hand-hexane and toluene were less efficient carbon sources for this bacterium.

In order to determine the *staphylococcus aureus* generation time in Luria Bertani broth, a growth curve research was conducted for the organism. It was discovered that *staphylococcus aureus* is a species that grows quickly. From the carbon source screening, fructose and maltose were used most effectively by *staphylococcus aureus*.

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REFERANCE

- [1] Brock, T. D., Madigan, M. T., Martinko, J. M., & Parker, J., *Brock biology of microorganisms*. Upper Saddle River (NJ): Prentice-Hall, 2003..
- [2] Kenneth Todar, PhD - Madison, Wisconsin, 2020.
- [3] Tong, M. *Effects of Carbon Metabolism on the growth of bacteria and antibiotic efficacy* (Doctoral dissertation).2022.
- [4] Missiakas DM, Schneewind O. *Growth and laboratory maintenance of Staphylococcus aureus*. Curr Protoc Microbiol. Feb;Chapter 9:Unit 9C.1. 2013.
- [5] Sánchez, S., Chávez, A., Forero, A., García-Huante, Y., Romero, A., Sánchez, M., & Ruiz, B. *Carbon source regulation of antibiotic production*. The Journal of antibiotics, 63(8), 442-459. 2010.
- [6] Kashid, S., Shrigadiwar, S., Zare, S., Joshi, K., & Nene, S. *Screening of Carbon Sources for Fragrance Producing Bacterial Species*.2021.